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ERROR ANALYSIS AS A PEDAGOGICAL TOOL IN THE TRANSLATION COURSE: THE FRENCH-GREEK LANGUAGE PAIR IN A UNIVERSITY ENVIRONMENT

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The present study treats translation errors which University students are capable of recognizing and correcting. A translated text in Greek, containing errors made on purpose, was proposed to students, who were asked to intervene. Some of those errors were successfully identified and rectified, while others were not. In some cases, the students intervened by rectifying translation units that were absolutely correct. The major hypothesis is whether this kind of exercise helps students realize dissymmetrical morphosyntactic and lexical uses and to what extent. We argue that the interest of such type of exercise is obvious, given that students act like readers, thus feeling more comfortable during the task assigned and, therefore, identify errors easier. As far as our results are concerned, it appears that our hypothesis is generally verified, although subject to some constraints.

Keywords: error analysis, didactics, translation, Modern Greek, French.

1. Introduction

In a comparative point of view, error analysis constitutes an exercise allowing to evaluate the learner's competence in the analysis of his mother tongue as well as of another language, when used in a translation course. In order to be able to help the student progress in their learning, the professor must know the kind of errors his student is expected not only to commit but also to recognize. He will be, thus, able to exploit the «pedagogy of error» (6, p.51).

The aim of the present article lies in constituting an attempt to study the reactions of learners exposed to the errors presented in a deliberately modified translation, process occurring during a translation examination. We mean to examine whether this kind of exercise helps learners to be more sensitive in regards to the errors they commit and to the mechanisms followed by their brain. It all comes to the technique of awareness, which aims at overcoming the obstacle of learners' motivation; technique which is both difficult and interesting, since, even though language is a part of culture, the challenge no longer consists in resorting to a word for word transposition (image quite generalized and apparently false that all translation students have), but in contesting every word that appears in the translation. This task invites learners to think more and be more sensitive as regards the difficulty and the subtlety of the translation process (11, p.218). This way, Wittgenstein's percept "the limits of my language mean the limits of my world" is being verified. Focus is concentrated not on linguistic competence but on the acquisition of cultural knowledge and intercultural abilities through the text and its contextualisation. This cultural approach of translation reminds us of Lotman's (14) position,

as expressed to his *Universe of the Mind. A Semiotic Theory of Culture*, that «the instrument of semiotic research is translation».

Apart from these preliminary remarks, more questions arise: how can we put an end to this erroneous perception students have that fidelity is irrelevant to the errors committed due to defective knowledge of the two linguistic systems? Students not used to this kind of task, how will they react? Will they be able to recognize the errors? Because of their lacking linguistic knowledge/background, will they characterize as errors translation units that are acceptable alternatives? We conclude that, even though promising, results appear rather deceiving, mainly because of the low level of students' language knowledge.

2. Méthodologie

Our study is based on a text written in French, Simone de Beauvoir's *Le Deuxième Sexe* (The second sex), written in 1949, put in contrast with its' Greek translation by Tzeni Konstantinou (*To Δεύτερο φύλο*). The translation used (hence *correct version*) within the framework of an examination for a translation course is the official translation. Another text (hence *modified translation*) was also given to students, containing the original translation, with some modifications, done by my colleague in the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Georges Varsos¹.

An extract of two texts (original of 156 words and Varsos' modified translation of 166 words) were given during an examination of translation to 3rd year and more of study in the Department of French Language and Literature, at the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens. The proposed, deliberately modified translation comported 15 errors, of which students had to detect 10, and subsequently propose a corrected version of those problematic translations.

We examined 145 copies. Let's notice that we didn't proceed to a quantitative analysis, since the exact number of students having made one or another error doesn't have any incidence on our study. On the contrary, our study is qualitative. This aspect is far more interesting, given that the phenomena studied are very recurrent. Accordingly, the modifications concerned repetitive phenomena and aimed at pointing the notion of *interférence* and its disastrous impact in translation. Students must be very cautious about their a priori and certainty (due to ignorance and to the mechanism of *analogy*, which are generally causing them) « and recognize that, in order for the translator to reach the right solution, he has to have previously evaluated all the alternatives which he has renounced» (11, p.219). Nevertheless, proceeding by trial and error seems to be a quite tedious challenge for the students who have the impression that translating must be done quickly and without implying very much thinking (11, p.227). We should therefore awaken to them «vigilance, requirements/ stringency/ expectation, intelligence and sensibility» (11, p.232). As for the nature of those modifications which were made, students should:

1) be awaken about the *false friends*, coming either from their mother tongue or, mainly, from the English language. It is also noteworthy the low level of even their mother tongue and the indubitable influence of the English language which spreads even more during this globalization era (17, p.523) (ex. 1, 2, 12).

2) recognize syntactic subtleties (ex. 6, 7, 8, 9).

With regard to the structure of our study, we shall first examine this new kind of exercise and its usefulness, in order to continue with the analysis of errors and our conclusions.

3. Theoretical notions

3.a Preliminaries

¹ I wish to thank George Varsos, my colleague in the Department of French Language and Literature, for allowing me to use the copies he got during the examination of his course *Introduction aux techniques de traduction* [Introduction to the techniques of translation].

If we consider a translation done during an examination in a translation class, it seems students are not aware of the extent of errors made, nor, of course, the recurrence of such errors. When explaining their mistakes to them, they acknowledge they have not internalized the proper use of translation units (morphological and semantic levels). They also acknowledge lacking a sufficient degree of assimilation of the French - and even Greek - languages knowledge and, for this reason, they have been compelled to act intuitively trying to establish equivalences. However, this principle of *reception/perception by intuition* is pernicious. The result is a word-for-word translation, where interferences with other languages are blatant.

3.b Is it a simple action or a reflection? The benefits of this type of exercise

Our experience as a translation teacher allows us to argue that giving learners a text to be translated, in order to correct it in class afterwards, does not help them fully be aware of their weaknesses. On the contrary, if we help them understand the origin of their errors, they acquire the means to avoid them later on (5, p.37). Hence the need for another type of exercise that can help raise awareness effectively among learners. This need was put forward by Ballard (2, p.256-257) who explains that: «The translation course should raise students' awareness of and expression of problems, but this can only be done through reflection and not simple action».

Errors thus serve as indicators of the relevant intellectual learning processes. As for the latter, it is above all a matter of inference, memorization, association, analogy, transfer, simplification and standardization, etc. (19, p.77) which produce interferences either from the mother tongue, English, or any other foreign language. By focusing on these interferences, the teacher can help learners be aware of language system asymmetries, thereby converging, if not preventing, at least reducing the number of errors made in the future. This learning approach makes errors much more positive. Collombat (5, p.40) argues that:

«The so-called "crystallized" intelligence grows with experience - the latter also comprising the errors made, especially as we offer ways of avoiding errors and identifying potential errors of this kind. [...] It is through this process that it is commonly agreed that translation is a "slowly maturing" profession: experience will always be recognized as a key to improvement and greater ability to address the problems encountered.

Ballard (2011) advocates this «new and constructive» behavior in relation to error, which involves detecting an error and comparing it to the «appropriate solution», as it leads to «an awakening or development of judgment and self-assessment skills on the part of the learner». Thus, Cuq's postulate (6, p.51) that through interferential errors «the learner gradually rebalances the foreign language system in him» is confirmed.

This type of exercise is very interesting, specifically because learners are not required to translate a text into their mother tongue, a task which is traditionally assigned in the translation course. This new type of exercise has also been proposed by Ballard (2, p.258) and its relevance is based on questions it raises among learners (5, p.41-42). If we give students a text with its translation and inform them that the translation has been modified, we put them in a state of *cognitive imbalance* (5, p.41-42) and encourage them to identify and correct the revised units. We urge them to solve a problem, to make a decision. In this way they are more motivated than they would be, if they were given a text to be translated. (12, p.260-261). It is worth noting that the awareness-raising approach is one of the two methods (other being marks through pressure) which seek to overcome one learner's barrier, that is, motivation.

Gile (12, p.260-261) perceived the importance of raising learners' awareness and its strong links with motivation. When addressing motivation issue, he explains that «creating situations where students themselves become readers, revisers or users of a translation and therefore are aware of all shortcomings without being themselves in a defensive position» will help them be aware of errors made. Based on this, we assume that the presentation of this text with its modified translation would help students find themselves in a more privileged position than they would be, if they were given a text to be translated, and they would not feel so threatened by the task, as they should act as

revisers/evaluators and not as students. Furthermore, this comparison will help them understand the specific structures of each of the languages under study and thus improve their linguistic and cultural knowledge.

4. Case studies analysis

Let us proceed with the analysis of the choices made by students. First of all, we should point out that all changes made by our colleague aim at assessing the learners' ability of not falling into the word-for-word and interference trap.

2.a First case study: mistranslations (such as false friends) that students can accurately detect:

French text	Modified translation	Accurately detected errors
(1) Toute l'éducation de la femme vise à lui barrer les chemins de la révolte	Η όλη εκπαίδευση της γυναίκας προσβλέπει ότι θα της φράξει τους δρόμους της αντίστασης [expects / relies on]	επιδιώκει να/αποσκοπεί στο να της φράξει τους δρόμους της αντίστασης [επιδιώκει and αποσκοπεί mean aim at]
(2) En somme, chaque sexe croit se justifier...	Αθροιστικά, το κάθε φύλο θεωρεί ότι δικαιώνεται [adding / totalling]	Καταλήγοντας/συνοψίζοντας/εν κατακλείδι/τελικά το κάθε φύλο θεωρεί ότι δικαιώνεται [in short/ in conclusion]
(3) chaque sexe croit se justifier en accusant l'autre	το κάθε φύλο θεωρεί ότι δικαιώνεται κατηγορώντας το διαφορετικό [the different]	το κάθε φύλο θεωρεί ότι δικαιώνεται κατηγορώντας το άλλο (φύλο)/τον άλλον [the other (sex) / others]

In these examples, words were misleading because of their graphic/phonetic similarity to false friends. Students were able to detect errors and replace them with equivalent translation units. Therefore, in (1), the modified verb *προσβλέπει*, meaning *expect/rely on*, was appropriately replaced by a verb expressing purpose, *επιδιώκει/αποσκοπεί* (*aim at*). This modification is meant to assess the learners' ability of not falling into the interference trap. As this verb is not much transparent for Greek learners and is similar to *vision*, (*in*)*visible* in English and French, it is a good example of a false friend.

The same applies to examples (2)-(3), where the modified segments have been detected and corrected: *En somme*, modified as *Αθροιστικά* (similar to the English *to sum up*), *l'autre* (meaning: *sex*) modified as *το διαφορετικό* (*the different*) have been respectively replaced by *καταλήγοντας/συνοψίζοντας* (*in conclusion*) and *το άλλο* (*l'autre*), to which some students found it necessary to add the noun *φύλο* (*sex*), in order to make explicit the referent that was not sufficiently clear to them.

In both examples, our students succeeded in detecting and correcting the modified translation units, proving that translating is no longer perceived as a pure linguistic task, consisting in a word for word substitution. It becomes a cultural skill, since it consists in transposing one culture into another, via the search of equivalence of translation units. Consequently, so far our hypothesis is being verified. The translations have also been modified at the syntactic level:

French text	Modified translation	Accurately detected errors
(4) Elle se laisse volontiers fasciner par l'espoir de	Και αφήνεται ευχαρίστως να γοητεύει με την ελπίδα ότι θα	Και αφήνεται ευχαρίστως να γοητεύεται με την ελπίδα ότι θα

pouvoir réaliser sa <i>vie sans rien faire</i> .	μπορέσει να πραγματοποιήσει τη ζωή της <i>δίχως καθόλου να το κάνει</i> . [without doing it at all]	μπορέσει να πραγματοποιήσει τη ζωή της <i>δίχως να κάνει τίποτε</i> . [without doing anything]
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In this case, the issue of reformulating some expressions was adequately addressed. So, in (4) students realized that the negation was related to the verb's complement *faire* (*rien faire*) and not to *réaliser*, an option put forward by the modified translation. This error helps assess learners' ability to detect the syntactic subtleties of their working languages.

2.b A second case study comprises mistranslations (lexical and syntactic) that go undetected and unnoticed.

French text	Modified translation (by G. Varsos)	Undetected/ Unnoticed Errors	Corrected version
(5) Quand un <i>conflit</i> éclate entre l'homme et la femme,	Όταν παρουσιάζεται <i>έκρηξη</i> ανάμεσα στον άντρα και τη γυναίκα, [when an explosion occurs]	Όταν παρουσιάζεται <i>έκρηξη</i> ανάμεσα στον άντρα και τη γυναίκα, [explosion]	... <i>μία διαμάχη/διένεξη</i> ανάμεσα στον άντρα και τη γυναίκα, [conflit / quarrel/ dispute]
(6) Il <i>lui</i> reproche de l'avoir acceptée.	Εκείνος <i>του</i> καταλογίζει ότι την αποδέχτηκε. [him_masculine]	Εκείνος <i>του</i> καταλογίζει ότι την αποδέχτηκε. [him_masculine]	Εκείνος <i>της</i> καταλογίζει ότι την αποδέχτηκε. [her_feminine]
(7) La société entière -à commencer par ses parents respectés- <i>lui ment</i> ...	Ολόκληρη η κοινωνία - πρέπει να αρχίζει από τους σεβαστούς γονείς της - της <i>ψεύδεται</i> ... [lies to him _ intrinsic pronominal verb without IOC]	Ολόκληρη η κοινωνία - να/ που αρχίζει από τους σεβαστούς γονείς της- της <i>ψεύδεται</i> ...	Ολόκληρη η κοινωνία - ξεκινώντας από/ αρχής γενομένης από τους σεβαστούς γονείς της - της <i>λέει ψέματα</i> ... [lies to him _ verbal phrase without IOC]

In these examples, the modified units have not been detected. In example (5), some students did not understand that the meaning of *conflit* is *διαμάχη/διένεξη* and not *έκρηξη*, whose equivalent is *explosion*. Hence, the modified unit remained unchanged. As for (6), the problem lies in the meaning of the personal pronoun *lui*, whose referent applies to both men and women. Part of the problem refers to the Greek pronoun *του*, which should be replaced by the feminine pronoun *της*, since its referent is «la femme». However, some students failed to find an appropriate referent, and used the masculine pronoun. However, this choice led to a non-sense (7, p.58); «the man blames himself» is semantically meaningless. The same goes for example (7): *της ψεύδεται* (*lui ment*) is ungrammatical, since the intrinsic pronominal verb does not receive an IOC. In these examples, it can be seen that learners fall

into the trap of obsessively splitting the text into words and not checking the grammaticality of their translation. This constitutes an evidence that understanding language is a part of culture. Otherwise, pragmatic misunderstandings would be impossible, nevertheless, translating.

4.c There is a third case: miscorrections or over-corrections at either the syntactic (ex. 8-10) or lexical (ex. 11-14) level.

French text	Modified translation (by G. Varsos)	Miscorrections / over-corrections	Correct version
(8) La société entière-à commencer par ses parents respectés- lui ment...	Ολόκληρη η κοινωνία -πρέπει να αρχίζει από τους σεβαστούς γονείς της-της ψεύδεται.. [should start with]	Ολόκληρη η κοινωνία-να/που αρχίζει από τους σεβαστούς γονείς της-της ψεύδεται.. [*to start with/which starts with]	Ολόκληρη η κοινωνία –ξεκινώντας από/ αρχής γενομένης από τους σεβαστούς γονείς της-της λέει ψέματα [starting with]
(9) C'est ainsi que, tout au long de sa vie...	Είναι έτσι που, σε όλο το μάκρος... [Thus]	Είναι λοιπόν που σε όλο το... [This means that]	Έτσι/Ετσι, λοιπόν/ Αυτός είναι ο λόγος που/ Γι' αυτό... [Thus (then) /This is the reason why]
(10) Elle se laisse volontiers fasciner par l'espoir de... [she is the one to be fascinated]	Αφήνεται ευχαρίστως να γοητεύει με την ελπίδα ότι... [she is the one who fascinates]	Αφήνεται εθελοντικά/ ηθελημένα/από μόνη της /εύκολα να γοητεύει/ να γοητεύεται με την ελπίδα ότι... [voluntarily/ of its own will/ easily]	Αφήνεται ευχαρίστως να γοητεύεται με την ελπίδα ότι... [she is the one to be fascinated]
(11) on élève la femme sans jamais lui enseigner la nécessité d'assumer elle-même son existence;	η γυναίκα διαπαιδαγωγείται χωρίς ποτέ να διδαχθεί τη βεβαιότητα να αναλάβει η ίδια την ευθύνη της ύπαρξής της. [certainty]	χωρίς ποτέ να διδαχθεί την χρησιμότητα/ ενδεχόμενο να αναλάβει η ίδια την ευθύνη της ύπαρξής της. [usefulness/ probability]	η γυναίκα διαπαιδαγωγείται χωρίς ποτέ να διδαχθεί την αναγκαιότητα/την ανάγκη/ότι είναι απαραίτητο να αναλάβει η ίδια την ευθύνη της ύπαρξής της. [necessity /need/necessary to]
(12) On ne m'a pas appris à raisonner, à gagner ma vie...	Δεν με μάθανε να υπολογίζω, να κερδίζω στη ζωή μου... [calculate/estimate/count]	Δεν με μάθανε να αντηχώ/να δικαιολογούμαι /να λογικεύομαι, να κερδίζω στη ζωή μου [resound/ justify oneself/reason with oneself]	Δεν με μάθανε να έχω λογική/να σκέφτομαι/να επιχειρηματολογώ, να κερδίζω στη ζωή μου... [be logical/good sense/think/argue]
(13) Quand un conflit éclate	Όταν παρουσιάζεται έκρηξη ανάμεσα στον	Όταν παρουσιάζεται έκρηξη ανάμεσα στον άντρα και τη γυναίκα,	Όταν δημιουργείται μία διαμάχη/διένεξη ανάμεσα

entre l'homme et la femme,	άντρα και τη γυναίκα, [<i>explosion</i>]	[<i>explosion</i>]	στον άντρα και τη γυναίκα [<i>conflict/quarrel /dispute</i>]
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In examples (8)-(9) we notice that there are some mistranslations. In (8), the error refers to the use of the infinitive and how it can be translated into Greek. More concretely, students understood that the suggested translation was wrong and should be corrected. However, their choice suggests that there is confusion as to the translation of the infinitive preceded by a preposition (*à commencer*). In other words, their erroneous choice stems from the incompatibility of both the construction *να + verb* and *που + verb* along with the circumstantial complement of way.

It is true that the structure *à + infinitive* appears above all to be a direct complement of a verb: *J'apprends à danser*, etc. The preposition *à* is then translated by the particle *να* (*Μαθαίνω να διαβάζω*). Apparently, this interference led our students to translate as *να αρχίζει από*. However, this meaning should be excluded, since the structure *à commencer par* is not a (direct or indirect) verb's complement. It is an infinitive structure expressing simultaneity (3, p.269). It is affixed and plays the role of a circumstantial complement of time, as it indicates «the circumstances in which an action was carried out (circumstantial complements of time, place, manner, cause, purpose, accompaniment, price, instrument, means, etc.) » (10, p.85). Riegel and allii (18, p.141) note that: «a circumstantial complement can be placed between a subject and a verb». That is our case, where the structure is inserted between the subject (*la société*) and the verb (*ment*). In addition, in French, this structure can be illustrated by a gerund, which also plays the role of a circumstantial complement (7, p.339).

This structure is symmetrically translated by means of an adverbial construction. In other words, this affixed circumstantial complement equals a gerund, hence its translation by a gerund/present participle *ξεκινώντας από* (*en commençant par*) or by a past participle (*αρχής γενομένης*).

In example (9), *C'est ainsi que* translated as *Είναι λοιπόν που*, this inappropriate choice results, once more, from a word-for-word translation. Extraction appears to be a misleading phenomenon (2, p.257). It is one of the most frequently «drop-off points» used by Greek learners. On the contrary, whereas in French the structure *C'est* («présentatif») + the constituent of the sentence (*ainsi*) + relative pronoun *que/qui* is acceptable according to French writing standards, using a word-for-word translation is a structure which is not specific to Greek. Therefore, the Greek utterance, if not unacceptable, at least it shows some barbarism. Learners were unable to identify the unpredictable and unsymmetrical nature of this structure proving that understanding language is a part of culture, the inappropriate/false acquisition of which leads to semantico-pragmatic misunderstandings.

Moreover, as regards example (10), apart from the lexical problem (see below about *volontiers*), we must also consider a morphosyntactic problem, referring to the voice. The trap consists in detecting that we are dealing with a factitious verb (18, p.228-231) and that the translation into Greek should be *αφήνεται ευχαρίστως να γοητεύεται*. The fact remains that, since the factive function of the construction, *se laisser + infinitive* is not identified, the translation is, once again, incorrect.

Here are some over-corrections at the lexical level: in example (10) the translation of the adverb *volontiers* as *εθελοντικά* (interference with the English *volunteer*) leads to a mistranslation². In (11), *nécessité* has nothing to do with *βεβαιότητα* (*certainty*)/ *χρησιμότητα* (*usefulness*) / *ενδεχόμενο* (*probability*), which is also a mistranslation. The same is true in (12), where the mistranslation is

² According to Delisle et al. (7, p.40), false sens is: « faute de traduction qui consiste à attribuer à un mot ou à une expression du texte de départ une acception erronée qui altère le sens du texte, sans pour autant conduire à un contresens [...] Le faux sens résulte habituellement de l'appréciation erronée de la <signification pertinente> d'un mot. Ce glissement de sens dû à une interprétation fautive conduit généralement à une <impropriété> [...] Le faux sens est une erreur moins grave qu'un contresens ou un non-sens, car il ne dénature pas complètement le sens du texte de départ. Néanmoins, la ligne de démarcation entre le faux sens et le contresens est parfois difficile à tracer. »

either due to the similarity to *résonner* or the confusion between the active and pronominal voice of the verbs *raisonner/se raisonner*.

Apart from the case of mistranslation, there are cases where there was an error in a unit that was not supposed to be corrected (over-correction). Specifically, students do not see the modified unit, but as they move towards the end, knowing that there is a specific number of errors to be detected, they work in a unit that did not raise any issue. Thus, in (13), some students replaced the verb *παρουσιάζεται/se présente, surgit* either by *σημειώνεται/a lieu* or *ξεσπάει/éclate* or by *παρατηρείται/est remarqué*, whereas the modified unit referred to the noun *conflict/σύγκρουση* translated as *έκρηξη/explosion*. However, students are not aware of the problem of translating this particular noun. There is therefore, once again, a mistranslation in the corrected translation.

We note that although we offer students the option of a ready-made translation, they are often unable to detect and correct errors. This implies that they have not reached yet the stage which Collombat (5, p.40) defines as the «required stage of maturation». In fact, students did not move «from a *paradigmatic* logic of word-for-word substitution to a *syntagmatic* logic of discourse realization in both languages» (5, p.48). Moreover, the presence of this type of action suggests that they have poor command of French and their mother tongue (12).

The teacher is faced with a situation of including grammatical exercises/ explanations in the translation course to remedy the lack of language skills (8, p.185-188). This phenomenon is unfortunately growing. In an attempt to address this, although the teacher may make any clarification beneficial to language teaching, it is still a limited and uncertain exercise, given the nature of translation. Therefore, because of the poor command of both language systems, the teacher must take into account the *geography of error* (8, p.257), in other words, to systematize all situations that are pitfalls for Greek learners (such as the use of determinant, infinitive, passive voice, pronoun on, thematization, etc.). This classification of errors will enable teachers to better adapt their teaching to the needs of the class (17, p.523).

This issue led to the creation of the *Contrastive Syntax and Translation* courses that have been included in the new University Program, recently implemented. This course, in order to address students' deficiencies, seeks to bring together tricky points (especially morphosyntax and lexical points) and to educate learners on the peculiarities of both language systems. It should be pointed out that in this course, apart from identifying and correcting errors, we ask learners to justify their choice, which is a method that encourages practice and reflection, «in-depth analysis and intuition». (11, p.218-219).

Conclusion

We have examined the translation errors that our university French language students were able to detect and correct. Whether there are errors that students are able to accurately detect, errors that go unnoticed, miscorrections or over-corrections, we have tried to examine the level of their awareness on the language system variations. We should not forget that frustrations basically arise, when the student cannot infer the right meaning of an utterance, because of his/her perception staying in the vocabulary/ grammar level without integrating both linguistic and extra linguistic features of the context of communication (15).

The decision to give students a text with its translation aimed at raising awareness among them without putting them in a defensive position, since they were not required to translate it by themselves. When acting as revisers, learners had more freedom and were far more motivated and aware of the need to avoid interferences that appeared in the modified translation.

However, practice has to some extent denied this assumption; the fact that students act as revisers sometimes is more a deterrent than a motivating factor, despite studies claiming the opposite (5, 12, 16 etc.). Consequently, our students didn't succeed in detecting all 15 modified errors. It seems that there is a further difficulty compared to the case where students act solely as translators of a text. This is due to the poor command of both language systems and especially their mother tongue, coupled with a tendency to translate quickly and thoughtlessly.

The benefit of this exercise is of great importance, as it has highlighted the need for a change in the teaching of translation; learners are trained to consider translation not as a simple switch of words from one language to another, idea generally internalized when it comes to translation process, but rather as a cultural skill, establishing equivalences among different world's views, as an awareness that only occurs when the learner has to ponder over the translation activity.

Our task is to sensitize our students on the fact that they must always ask themselves the question on the acceptability of selected translation unit by practicing what Delisle and René (8, p.124) call «methodical doubt». When addressing critical issues, the differences between the languages under study, the course is much more focused. We analyze errors and encourage our students to ask themselves questions, to be aware of the fact that languages may have more discrepancies than similarities, giving rise to semantico-pragmatic misunderstandings, and therefore to be more focused.

Based on our experience as a teacher of this course since 2011, it was undeniable that there was an improvement in the awareness of this type of pitfalls. It would be advisable to carry out a quantitative and more detailed study showing this slow maturation. This is still to be done.

Bibliographic references:

- 1) BALLARD, Michael (études réunies par) (2009), *Traductologie et enseignement de traduction à l'Université*. Arras: Artois Presses Université
- 2) BALLARD, Michael (2011), « Opération vérité pour la traduction dans l'enseignement supérieur ». In : T. Milliaressi (éd.), *De la linguistique à la traductologie. Interpréter/traduire*, Villeneuve d'Ascq: Presses Universitaires du Septentrion, p. 253-270
- 3) BECHADE, Henri (1986). *Syntaxe du français moderne et contemporain*. Paris: PUF
- 4) BESSE, Henri (1970), « Problèmes de sens dans l'enseignement d'une langue étrangère ». In: *Langue Française*, vol. 8, n. 8, p. 62-77
- 5) COLLOMBAT, Isabelle (2009), « La didactique de l'erreur dans l'apprentissage de la traduction ». In: *The Journal of Specialised Translation*, 12, p. 37-54
- 6) Cuq, Jean-Pierre (1996), *Une introduction à la didactique de la grammaire en français langue étrangère*, Paris: Didier/Hatier
- 7) DELISLE, Jean, LEE-JAHNKE, Hannelore, CORMIER, Michael (1999), *Terminologie de la traduction*, Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins
- 8) DELISLE, Jean, RENE, Alain (2003), *La Traduction raisonnée : manuel d'initiation à la traduction professionnelle de l'anglais vers le français : méthode par objectifs d'apprentissage*, Ottawa: Les Presses de l'Université d'Ottawa
- 9) DEBUSER, Francis (1970), « La Linguistique Contrastive et les Interférences ». In : *Langue Française*, vol. 8, n 8, p. 31-61
- 10) DUBOIS, Jean (sous la direction) (1994), *Dictionnaire de Linguistique et des sciences du langage*, Paris : Larousse
- 11) FONTANET, Mathilde (2009), « Enseignement de la traduction : Recherche d'un équilibre sensible ». In M. Ballard, *Traductologie et enseignement de traduction à l'Université*, Arras : Artois Presses Université, p. 217-233
- 12) GEMAR, Jean-Claude (1995), *Traduire ou l'art d'interpréter*. Canada : Presses Universitaire du Québec
- 13) GILE, Daniel (1992), « Les fautes de traduction : une analyse pédagogique ». In: *Meta*, vol. 37, n 2, p. 251-262
- 14) LAMPROU, Efi & FLOROS, G. (2010), *Η διδακτική της μετάφρασης στον ελληνόφωνο χώρο. Σύγχρονες τάσεις και προοπτικές* [The didactics of translation in the hellenophone space. Modern tendencies and perspectives], Athens: Ellinika Grammata
- 15) LOTMAN, Yuri (1990), *Universe of the Mind. A Semiotic Theory of Culture*. Bloomington and Indianapolis: Indiana University Press

16) OBDALOVA, O.A., MINAKOVA, L.Y., TIKHONOVA, E.V., SOBOLEVA, A.V. (2018), «Insights into Receptive Processing of Authentic Foreign Discourse by EFL Learners». In: Filchenko A., Anikina Z. (eds) *Linguistic and Cultural Studies: Traditions and Innovations*. LKTI 2016. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing, vol 677. Springer, Cham

17) PARIANOU, Anastasia (2010), « Διδακτική της ειδικής μετάφρασης: λειτουργική προσέγγιση και περιφερειακές γλώσσες » [Didactics of specialised translation: functional approach and peripheral languages]. In: E. Lamprou & G. Floros, *Η διδακτική της μετάφρασης στον ελληνόφωνο χώρο. Σύγχρονες τάσεις και προοπτικές* [The didactics of translation in the hellenophone space. Moderne tendencies and perspectives], Athens: Ellinika Grammata, p. 95-114

18) PATERAKI-CHATZIADONIOU, Olga (2004), « Apprentissage du FLE: difficultés rencontrées par les étudiants grecs et propositions de remèdes ». In: Actes du 5ème Congrès Panhellénique des Professeurs de français, Athènes, p. 509-524

19) RIEGEL, Martin, PELLAT Jean-Christophe, RIOUL René (1994), *Grammaire Méthodique du Français*, Paris: PUF

20) VALENZUELA, Oscar (2010), « La didactique des langues étrangères et les processus d'enseignement/apprentissage ». In: *Synergies Chili*, 6, p. 71-86

Appendices

Simone de Beauvoir, <i>Le deuxième sexe</i>	Translation modified by G. Varsos
Toute l'éducation de la femme vise à lui barrer les chemins de la révolte et de l'aventure ; la société entière - à commencer par ses parents respectés - lui ment en exaltant la haute valeur de l'amour et du dévouement et en lui cachant que ni l'amant, ni le mari, ni les enfants ne seront disposés à en supporter la charge encombrante.	Η όλη εκπαίδευση της γυναίκας προσβλέπει ότι θα της φράξει τους δρόμους της αντίστασης και της περιπέτειας· ολόκληρη η κοινωνία - πρέπει να αρχίζει από του σεβαστούς γονείς της - της ψεύδεται εκθειάζοντας την υψηλή αξία της αγάπης και της αφοσίωσης και αποκρύβοντάς της ότι ούτε ο εραστής, ούτε ο σύζυγος, ούτε τα παιδιά θα έχουν τη διάθεση να της σηκώσουν το υπέρογκο φορτίο.
C'est ainsi que, tout au long de sa vie, on élève la femme sans jamais lui enseigner la nécessité d'assumer elle-même son existence ; et elle se laisse volontiers fasciner par l'espoir de pouvoir réaliser sa vie sans rien faire.	Είναι έτσι που, σε όλο το μάκρος της ζωής της, η γυναίκα διαπαιδαγωγείται δίχως ποτέ να διδαχθεί τη βεβαιότητα να αναλάβει η ίδια την ευθύνη της ύπαρξής της· και αφήνεται ευχαρίστως να γοητεύει με την ελπίδα ότι θα μπορέσει να πραγματώσει τη ζωή της δίχως καθόλου να το κάνει.
Quand un conflit éclate entre l'homme et la femme, chacun tient l'autre pour responsable de la situation. Elle lui reproche de l'avoir créée : « on ne m'a pas appris à raisonner, à gagner ma vie... ». Il lui reproche de l'avoir acceptée : « tu ne sais rien, tu es une incapable ».	Όταν παρουσιάζεται έκρηξη ανάμεσα στον άντρα και τη γυναίκα, ο ένας ρίχνει στον άλλον την ευθύνη της κατάστασης. Εκείνη τον κατηγορεί ότι τη δημιούργησε: «δεν με μάθανε να υπολογίζω, να κερδίζω στη ζωή μου...». Εκείνος του καταλογίζει ότι την αποδέχτηκε: «δεν ξέρεις τίποτα, μια ανίκανη είσαι».
En somme, chaque sexe croit se justifier en accusant l'autre.	Αθροιστικά, το κάθε φύλο θεωρεί ότι δικαιώνεται κατηγορώντας το διαφορετικό.